

Vanadium. Part VIII. Infrared Studies of Some Vanadium Complexes

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A study of the IR spectral characteristics of a series of vanadyl chelates has been made. The reasons for the lowering of the vanadyl stretching frequencies of vanadium (IV) and of vanadium (V) complexes have been discussed.

Isolation and characterisation of a large number of vanadium chelates in the oxidation states, +5, +4, and +3, have already been described¹. Since Barraclough *et al.*² observed the stretching frequencies of V=O bond to lie between 960 and 1020 cm^{-1} in a number of vanadyl salts and complexes, it was considered of interest to study the IR spectra of the complexes prepared by us¹. Nakamoto *et al.*³ observed a decrease of 32 cm^{-1} in the V=O stretching frequency in the complex $[\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2(\text{py})]$, compared to $[\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2]$. This decrease has been attributed to a strong binding between the donor nitrogen atom of the pyridine and vanadium rather than a simple association of pyridine. McGlynn *et al.*⁴ have observed similar trends in the V=O stretching frequency with a number of ligands. They used the variation in the symmetric and antisymmetric stretching vibration of UO_2^{2+} in presence of different ligands to establish a ligand series similar to the spectrochemical series.

The vanadyl stretching frequencies of some of the complexes, prepared by us, along with some data of a few similar compounds, taken from the literature, are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Compounds.	Str. frequency (cm^{-1} .)	Compounds.	Str. frequency (cm^{-1} .)
$[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5]\text{SO}_4$	1020, 1004 ⁵	$[\text{VO}(\text{OH})\text{B}_2]$	968
$\text{VOF}_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$	9905	$[\text{VO}(\text{OMe})\text{B}_2]$	966
$(\text{NH}_4)_3[\text{VOF}_6]$	946, 934 ⁵	$[\text{VO}\text{T}_2]$	999, 980 sh
$[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Q}_2]$	977	$[\text{VO}(p\text{-Me-T})_2]$	978, 963 sh
(a) $[\text{VO}(\text{py})\text{Q}_2]\text{H}_2\text{O}$	963	$[\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2]$	996
(b) $[\text{VO}(\text{py})\text{Q}_2]$	970	$[\text{VO}(\text{oxin})_2]$	9775
$[\text{VO}(\text{OH})\text{Q}_2]2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	939	$[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{oxin})_2]$	952 ⁶
$[\text{VO B}_2]$	993, 974 sh	$[\text{VO}(\text{OEt})(\text{oxin})_2]$	9527

QH = quinsidinic acid; py = pyridine; BH = benzohydroxamic acid; TH = 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyl-triazene; acacH = acetylacetonone; oxinH = 8-hydroxyquinoline; *p*-Me-TH = 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-methyl-phenyltriazene.

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1. Dutta and Lahiry, *Science & Culture*, 1960, 26, 139; *Chem. & Ind.*, 1961, 78; this *Journal*, 1961, 38, 1001; 1962, 39, 871, 860; 1963, 40, 53, 67, 857, 863.
2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3552.
3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4533.
4. *J. Chem. Phys.* 1961, 35, 105.
5. Selbin *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1961, 748.
6. Bielig and Bayer, *Annalen*, 1953, 584, 96.
7. Blair *et al.*, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, 5, 316.

In order to explain the shift of V—O stretching vibrations in different complexes, it is important to consider (a) the packing effect in the lattice and (b) the coupling of vanadyl stretching with vanadium ligand vibrations. The effect (a) cannot be neglected, at least in the case of complexes with quinaldinic acid as the ligand, where most of the compounds are insoluble in common organic solvents and when their actual molecular sizes are unknown. For the effect (b), McGlynn *et al.*⁴ have observed that for the ligand mass exceeding 40 atomic mass unit, this is rather unimportant.

The ligand-vanadium bond may be of σ and π types and in absence of detailed structural data for these compounds, we would content ourselves with a qualitative picture of the effects of these σ and π bonds rather than evaluation of the more quantitative effects of them, as has been done by Ballhausen and Gray⁵ and less rigorously by McGlynn *et al.*⁴ The strength of the V=O bond depends on the oxygen $p\pi$ to metal $d\pi$ donation and since the electron density on the small oxygen atom is extremely high, the donation of electrons from oxygen to vanadium(IV), which has empty acceptor orbital, can take place. The degree of donation of electrons will be dependent on the acceptor properties of the metal orbital.

When a ligand with a strong σ donor capacity is bound to the vanadium, there will be two major effects:

(i) An increase of electron density in the metal orbital, which will have decreased the electron-acceptor property of the metal orbital. This will cause a decrease of oxygen $p\pi$ to metal $d\pi$ donation, resulting in a decrease of the V=O stretching frequency.

(ii) There will also occur an increase of electronic charge in a metal orbital, which is not involved in covalent-bond formation with the axial oxygen and will result in a strong repulsion with the highly negative oxygen with an effective weakening of the V=O bond.

The effect (ii) will be more important in passing from a higher to a lower valence state.

Both the effects will result in a lowering of the V=O stretching frequency and the decrease will be greater, the greater the donor ability of the ligand. This lowering may serve as a rough guide of the complexing ability of the ligands. On this basis, the ligands, listed in Table I, can be arranged in the following order of increasing σ -donor capacity:

It is pertinent to mention here Gillespie's observation⁶ that the strong repulsion between the electron pairs on the small fluorine atom causes them to be partially delocalised into the empty orbital of the bonded atom. This would then, according to our earlier reasoning, will lower the vanadyl stretching frequency.

In view of the above discussions, the lowering of the VO stretch in the oxo-hydroxo-vanadium (V) complexes, compared to the oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes (Table I), is quite interesting. Whereas according to McGlynn *et al.*⁴ there should have been an increase,

8. *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 111.

9. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 5978.

we really find a decrease in the series of quinaldinic acid, benzohydroxamic acid, and 8-hydroxyquinoline complexes with the introduction of a negative hydroxo or alkoxo group. It may be explained as follows. It is not unreasonable to assume that the total electron-accepting ability of a metal ion in a particular valence state is certain. When a V^{4+} complex changes to a V^{5+} complex, the vanadium ion increases its electro π -accepting character. At this stage, when a unidentate negative group reaches the co-ordination zone, it may or may not exactly counterbalance the increased electro π -accepting character of V^{5+} . If the donor property of the new ligand is greater than the increased acceptor property of the metal ion, there will be an overall accumulation of increased electron density around the vanadium ion. This would greatly affect $V=O$ bond, the stretching frequency of which would certainly be lowered. This is what we have found in the above series of complexes. Further, when a V^{4+} is oxidised to V^{5+} , the metal d orbital has no electron, so that the effect (ii), mentioned earlier, will be negligible. This should have been reflected by an increase in the $V=O$ stretch. Such a behaviour has been observed by McGlynn *et al.*⁴ in the decrease of $\approx 100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the metal—oxygen stretching frequency in passing from UO_2^{2+} and AmO_2^{2+} to UO_2^+ and AmO_2^+ .

The complexes, prepared by us, however, are not entirely parallel in composition to those of McGlynn *et al.*⁴. We feel that further studies with complexes of the type $[VO(OH)]^+$ and $[VO(OH)]^{2+}$ may offer a more rigorous testing of their observations.

Finally, the effect of co-ordination of pyridine in $[VO(py)Q_2]$ on the $V=O$ stretching frequency is reflected in a small decrease by 7.14 cm^{-1} , unlike 32 cm^{-1} in the $[VO(py)acac]$ complex. Since we could study the effect of pyridine co-ordination in only one complex, it is not possible for us to elaborate on this aspect of the complex formation at this stage.

While the results of this investigation were being composed for publication, Selbin *et al.*¹⁰ published their results on the effect of ligands on the $V=O$ stretching frequency. The reasons advanced are similar to those offered by McGlynn *et al.*⁴ for uranyl complexes. Further, they have not studied the effect of co-ordination of OH^- , OMe^- or OEt^- on the $V=O$ stretching frequency, especially in quinquevalent vanadium complexes.